

Table 2. Resistance to RSV of F₂, Yunnan Province, China, 1988.

Cross	F ₂ plants observed (no.)			χ ² for 3:1 ^a
	R	S	Total	
Zhongguo 91/Huxuan 19	75	19	94	1.149
Huxuan 19/Zhongguo 91	53	20	73	0.224
Zhongguo 91/Shuangfeng 1	77	33	110	1.467
Shuangfeng 1/Zhongguo 91	121	39	160	0.033
Fengfeng/683 Nuo	99	41	140	1.371
683 Nuo/Fengfeng	82	31	113	0.357
Huxuan 19/Fengfeng	103	14	117	10.794**
Shuangfeng 1/Tetep	76	39	115	4.873**

*** = significant difference at P < 0.01 by χ².

Reaction of rice cultivars from Ifugao Province, Philippines, to indigenous strains of the bacterial blight (BB) pathogen

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BB, caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo), is endemic in the mountainous Ifugao Province, Philippines. All of the Xoo strains tested from Ifugao have been typed as race 5 on differential rice cultivars IR24 (carrying no resistance genes), IR20 (*Xa-4*), IR1545-339 (*xa-5*), DV85 (*xa-5* and *Xa-7*), and CAS209 (*Xa-10*).

Greater diversity has been recognized among race 5 strains based on DNA typing. We conducted this study to assess the reaction of traditional Ifugao rice cultivars to Ifugao Xoo strains representing different DNA types of race 5.

Strain PXO 80 was collected in 1975, PXO 112 in 1978, and PXO 154 in 1981 from Banaue, Ifugao. DNA analysis using the repetitive DNA probes pJEL101 and pTNX1 showed strains PXO 80 and PXO 112 as closely related, while PXO 154 was more distantly related. Viable seed of 361 accessions of traditional cultivars were obtained from the International Rice Germplasm Center, IRRI.

Three hills per cultivar were planted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in screenhouse plots

and arranged in rows according to accession number. Plants were inoculated with one each of the three Xoo strains at late maximum tillering stage using the clipping method. Lesion lengths and percent diseased leaf area were measured at 14 and 21 d after inoculation.

Nearly 9% of the accessions were either susceptible or highly susceptible to the three strains; 80% were moderately susceptible or susceptible; 1.7% were

dominant to moderate when varieties of each type were crossed (Table 1).

We analyzed segregation of F₂ according to expected values of a pair of genes and χ² test (Table 2). Six of the eight F₂ populations had segregation ratios of resistance that fit the expected values (P > 0.05). The two other populations did not (P < 0.01). □

moderately resistant to moderately susceptible, or resistant to moderately susceptible; several were moderately resistant to resistant; and a few showed differential reactions (Table 1).

To confirm the differential reactions observed, 32 selected accessions were again inoculated. Differential reactions were not confirmed for most of them because it appeared that some were from mixed seed.

Table 1. Accessions of traditional cultivars from Ifugao Province, Philippines, showing resistant (R) or moderately resistant (MR) reactions, and one accession showing differential reaction to three strains of Xoo from the Philippines.

Accession no.	Lesion length ^a (cm)			Rating
	PXO 80	PXO 112	PXO 145	
8035	1.36	7.92	10.36	R
8077	1.48	6.08	9.72	R
8111	1.41	5.91	8.82	R
8162	1.90	10.80	8.31	R
8164	1.04	10.32	11.60	R/MR
9134	1.18	14.12	8.78	R
11226	7.15	6.22	14.41	MR
11282	6.29	6.53	15.39	MR
11306	4.58	4.59	3.12	R
12060	2.44	3.21	10.15	R
23354	0.72	0.62	0.87	R
23362	13.10	10.10	25.27	MR
60611	1.28	3.56	7.07	R/MR
60613	2.89	10.18	20.00	R/MR
8106 (differential)	2.15	11.06	58.86	R/MR

^aAv of measurements from 2-5 leaves for each of 3 plants.

Table 2. Reaction of selected lines from Acc. 8106 to selected strains of Xoo representing different RFLP types.

Parental plant no.	Progeny tested (no.)	Reaction ^a to race 5 strains of Xoo			
		PXO 80	PXO 112	PXO 154	PXO 144
1	15	R	R	S	S
2	15	R	R	S	S
3	15	R	R	S	S
4	15	R	R	S	S
5	15	S	S	S	S

^aR: lesion lengths of 0-10.0 cm at 14 d after inoculation; S: lesion lengths greater than 20.0 cm at 14 d after inoculation.

Accession 8106 demonstrated seed heterogeneity based on seed characteristics, disease reaction, and restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) analysis of selected lines. DNA from 14 derived lines was digested with the restriction enzyme EcoRV and probed with 23 RFLP markers. Markers RG554 and RG476 revealed polymorphisms between lines. The two polymorphic probes detected three and five

heterozygotes, respectively. This suggested that 8106 was segregating.

Thirty-three progeny of 8106 were inoculated with several Xoo strains per plant. We observed a range of reaction patterns in different progeny with some plants showing differential reaction consistent with the first experiment. For five of these plants, 15 progeny each were tested with PXO 80, PXO 112, and PXO 145. The differential reaction of some of the families was confirmed (Table 2).

The differentiation of Xoo strains by inoculation on derivatives of 8106 (designated "8106-R") suggests that race 5 may consist of more than one race. It further suggests that 8106-R contains a resistance gene not present in the differential set used for race typing of these strains. Further testing is required to determine whether the lines derived from acc. 8106 contain a novel resistance gene. □

Quantifying rice-leaf blast (Bl) genetic relationship via the receptivity factor

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Host-pathogen relationships, such as that of the rice-*Pyricularia grisea* pathosystem, have genetic as well as epidemiological components. The specificity of the association between rice and *P. grisea* may be estimated through the receptivity factor (RF).

We conducted three glasshouse experiments at IRRI during the 1990 wet and 1991 dry seasons using susceptible lowland cultivars IR50 and IR72, moderately resistant upland variety UPLRi-5, and resistant variety Kinandang Patong. Seeds were sown in plastic cups. One plant per cup was maintained and fertilized with the equivalent of 120 kg N/ha.

Twenty plants/variety were inoculated with PO6-6, a local isolate of *P. grisea*. Inoculum suspension was sprayed on slides coated with plain agar and placed on a rotating platform of an electrically operated spore-settling tower device. Samples of the slides were fixed on healthy test plant leaves (one slide per leaf) using a spore concentration of 1.5×10^5 /ml, 1 min spraying time, and 10 psi spraying pressure.

We counted the spores deposited on other slides to estimate deposition on leaves. This procedure was repeated at 10, 25, 40, and 55 d after sowing. Control plants were treated with sterile distilled water. Lesions on all inoculated leaves were assessed immediately after symptoms appeared.

1. RF values of blast-infected IR50, IR72, UPLRi-5, and Kinandang Patong (KP).

RF value per plant at different ages was estimated:

$$RF = \frac{\text{no. of lesions produced on the plant}}{\text{no. of spores deposited on the plant}}$$

RF values of the varieties studied were highest in IR50. IR72 and IR50 showed a trend of declining RF in which younger leaves showed high susceptibility to Bl (Fig. 1). UPLRi-5 produced a significantly different RF trend as leaves aged:

2. Linearized RF values of IR50 and IR72.

seedlings at 25 DAS showed more susceptibility to the disease than at any other age. Kinandang Patong was not infected at all.

IR50 was more susceptible than IR72 to Bl at all ages studied. RF in IR72 decreased faster relative to IR50 as crops aged (Fig. 2). Both varieties are considered susceptible to Bl. Our results suggest, however, that virulent pathogen isolates would cause more damage to IR50 than IR72 under field conditions favoring polycycles. RF values seem essential to accurately classify degrees of varietal resistance to *P. grisea*. □

Pest resistance—insects

Yield loss due to major rice pests in Tamil Nadu, India

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We assessed the yield loss caused by gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) Mani, yellow stem borer (YSB)

Scirpophaga incertulas Walker, and leafhopper (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenee on five rice varieties at Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai, during 1988-89. IR20, ADT36, MDU3, Sonalika, and IET9689 were raised under irrigated transplanted conditions during Jun-Sep and Oct-Jan.

We calculated yield loss for infestation at tillering, panicle initiation, and maturity (see table). IR20 suffered